

LIFE STORIES THROUGHOUT HISTORY: BIOARCHAEOLOGICAL NARRATIVES FROM ISOLA SACRA

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Abstract *The Isola Sacra necropolis, located in the Tiber delta near Ostia and Portus Romae, represents one of the most important bioarchaeological assemblages of the Roman Imperial period in central Italy. Excavated extensively during the twentieth century, the cemetery developed between the first and third centuries CE along the Via Flavia and primarily served the harbour population associated with the port complex of Portus.*

This study focuses on a sample of 94 adult crania curated at the Museum of Anthropology “G. Sergi” (Sapienza University of Rome), integrating legacy osteological data collected since the 1980s with newly generated biomolecular evidence within the framework of the CHANGES project. A key objective of the research is to integrate heterogeneous datasets through the digital IULLA database, enabling the combination of archaeological, anthropological, and biochemical information within a unified analytical framework.

In addition to traditional macroscopic analyses, new biomolecular investigations, including stable isotope analyses ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{15}\text{N}$, $\delta^{34}\text{S}$), strontium isotope analyses, radiocarbon dating, and amelogenin peptide analyses, have been undertaken to explore diet, mobility, chronology, and biological sex within the harbour population. Preliminary results include the spatial reassociation of museum-curated crania with specific funerary monuments along the Via Flavia, based on archival and collection-based research.

By reconnecting skeletal remains with their archaeological context and integrating osteological and biomolecular evidence, this study establishes the first comprehensive bioarchaeological framework for investigating the life histories and social dynamics of the Portus harbour community.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. The necropolis of Isola Sacra

The Isola Sacra necropolis takes its name from the river island on which it stands in the Tiber delta, approximately 23 km from Rome (Fig. 1). The site occupies the northern portion of the island formed between the Tiber River and the *Fossa Traiana*, the artificial canal that connected the river with the Tyrrhenian Sea. This funerary area developed between the 1st and 3rd centuries CE along a stretch of approximately 1.5 km of the ancient *Via Flavia*, the road linking Ostia to Portus Romae.

The emergence and expansion of the necropolis were closely connected to the development of the harbour complex of Portus¹. During the early Imperial period, Rome represented the principal commercial centre of the Mediterranean, relying heavily on maritime supply routes for food and other commodities. Because the harbour of Ostia was increasingly affected by silting, Emperor Claudius initiated the construction of a new port approximately 3 km north of the Tiber mouth between 42 and 64 CE. This harbour, known as *Portus Ostiensis Augusti*, consisted of a large basin protected by curved moles and dominated by a monumental lighthouse. In the early 2nd century CE, the port was further expanded under Trajan with the construction of the well-known hexagonal basin, transforming Portus into the primary maritime hub supplying the capital².

The development of this major harbour complex stimulated the growth of an extensive settlement around the port, inhabited by merchants, administrators, craftsmen, and workers involved in maritime

Figure 1. Geographical location of the Isola Sacra site in Latium.

¹ ANGELUCCI, BALDASSARRE, BRAGANTINI, LAURO, MANNUCCI, MAZZOLENI, MORSELLI, TAGLIETTI, 1990; BALDASSARRE, 1978; ID, 1980; ID, 1984; ID, 1990; BALDASSARRE, BRAGANTINI, DOLCIOTTI, MORSELLI, TAGLIETTI, 2018; BALDASSARRE, BRAGANTINI, DOLCIOTTI, MORSELLI, TAGLIETTI, TALONI, 1985; OLIVANTI, SPANU, 2018; SPERDUTI, 1995.

² BECATTI, RUSSELL, 1961; CALZA, BECATTI, 1974; MCWHIRR, 1989; OLESON, 2007.

trade³. The Isola Sacra necropolis served primarily the middle and lower social groups associated with this harbour community. Its location along the *Via Flavia* ensured high visibility, and the monumental tombs constructed along the road appear to have been intentionally positioned to display funerary architecture and commemorative inscriptions to passers-by⁴.

The necropolis was first identified in the early twentieth century during land reclamation works carried out in the Tiber delta. These accidental discoveries revealed a group of funerary buildings that now form the northern core of the cemetery. More extensive excavations were conducted between 1925 and 1940 under the direction of the archaeologist Calza, uncovering a large funerary area to the south and demonstrating the existence of a single, extensive necropolis located opposite the city of Portus⁵. Subsequent archaeological investigations carried out between 1973 and 1982 under the direction of the archaeologist Baldassarre focused on the western sector of the site and on the architectural and spatial organisation of the funerary complex. These excavations documented more than one hundred monumental family tombs, typically square in plan and covered by barrel vaults, belonging to the so-called *cell* architectural type, sometimes surrounded by enclosure walls. The remains of approximately one thousand individuals were recovered from these structures, many of which had originally housed collective burials within *arcosolia* that collapsed over time.

A further emergency excavation conducted between 1988 and 1989 aimed to address problems caused by the rising water table, which threatened the preservation of the monuments. This intervention investigated the areas between the monumental tombs and revealed a large number of non-monumental burials, approximately 670 graves, dating mainly to the Antonine period (c. 150–180 CE). These burials displayed a wide variety of depositional practices, including simple pit graves, *alla cappuccina* burials, amphora burials, wooden coffins, masonry cists, and terracotta containers.

³ MCWHIRR, 1989.

⁴ ANGELUCCI, BALDASSARRE, BRAGANTINI, LAURO, MANNUCCI, MAZZOLENI, MORSELLI, TAGLIETTI, 1990; BALDASSARRE, 1984; BALDASSARRE, 1990; BALDASSARRE, BRAGANTINI, DOLCIOTTI, MORSELLI, TAGLIETTI, 2018; OLIVANTI, SPANU, 2018.

⁵ CALZA, 1940.

Archaeological evidence indicates that the necropolis remained in use between the 1st and 3rd centuries CE and developed through several phases corresponding broadly to the Trajanic–Hadrianic, Antonine and Severan periods (Fig. 2). While the monumental tombs were arranged along the Via Flavia to maximise visibility, the simpler burials identified during later excavations were distributed irregularly in the spaces between these structures. As a result, the necropolis appears to have evolved progressively without a rigid urban plan, reflecting the dynamic growth of the harbour community it served⁶.

Figure 2. Integrated map of the monumental tombs of Isola Sacra (updated after Baldassarre, 1987).

2. THE SKELETAL COLLECTION

The skeletal material examined for this research comprises 94 adult crania, dated between the 1st and 3rd centuries CE, belonging to individuals considered to represent the middle-class population of *Portus Romae*. Secure associations with mandibles or postcranial remains are lacking due to depositional and post-depositional disturbances. These remains are preserved at the Museum of Anthropology “G. Sergi”, Sapienza University of Rome⁷. The study integrates data collected since the 1980s with newly acquired biochemical and biomolecular evidence.

2.1. Previous bioarchaeological research on the Isola Sacra population

The large number of individuals recovered from the Isola Sacra necropolis and the overall good preservation of the skeletal material have made this assemblage one of the most extensively studied bioarchaeological collections from the Roman Imperial period in central Italy. Over the past decades, numerous anthropological investigations have explored different aspects of the life conditions of the

⁶ ANGELUCCI, BALDASSARRE, BRAGANTINI, LAURO, MANNUCCI, MAZZOLENI, MORSELLI, TAGLIETTI, 1990; BALDASSARRE, 1984; ID., 1990; ID., 2018; OLIVANTI, SPANU, 2018.

⁷ SPERDUTI, 1995.

harbour population associated with Portus Romae, including biological variability, health status, diet, mobility, and daily activities⁸.

Early anthropological studies focused on biological variability within the population. Analyses of cranial morphometric traits demonstrated that the Isola Sacra sample displays a relatively homogeneous biological profile, suggesting a fairly cohesive population structure associated with the port community of Portus Romae⁹. Dental morphological studies have further supported this interpretation, indicating limited biological variability consistent with a socially defined urban population often interpreted as representing the “middle class” of the harbour settlement¹⁰.

Later research shifted attention to indicators of physiological stress and health conditions. The presence of enamel hypoplasia and Harris lines has been interpreted as evidence of episodic physiological stress during growth, likely linked to nutritional fluctuations, disease exposure, and environmental pressures typical of densely populated harbour environments¹¹. These stress markers may reflect the unstable food supply characteristic of large urban centres of the Roman Empire, as well as environmental factors associated with the Tiber delta, including the presence of malaria and potential exposure to lead contamination¹².

Other osteological markers have provided insights into daily activities and aspects of social life. In particular, a relatively high frequency of auditory exostoses has been documented among male individuals from the necropolis. These bony growths of the external auditory canal are commonly associated with repeated exposure to cold water and are often interpreted as evidence of frequent bathing or water-related activities, which were likely part of everyday life in the harbour environment of Portus¹³. Palaeopathological studies have also investigated dental health and metabolic conditions within the population. Comparisons with other archaeological samples from central Italy have shown that individuals from Isola Sacra generally display lower frequencies of dental pathologies and porotic lesions than populations from later historical periods, suggesting broader changes in diet and living conditions between the Roman Imperial period and the early Middle Ages¹⁴.

More recent research has increasingly employed biomolecular approaches to reconstruct diet, mobility, and life history. Stable isotope analyses of carbon and nitrogen have demonstrated that the inhabitants of Isola Sacra consumed a mixed diet primarily based on terrestrial resources, including C3 plants and animal proteins, supplemented by a significant contribution from marine foods¹⁵. It should be noted, however, that the isotopic dataset published by Prowse and colleagues was derived from a slightly

⁸ ARGENTI, MANZI, 1988; MANZI, SPERDUTI, 1988; MANZI, SANTANDREA, PASSARELLO, 1997; PROWSE, SCHWARCZ, SAUNDERS, MACCHIARELLI, BONDIOLI, 2004; PROWSE, SCHWARCZ, SAUNDERS, MACCHIARELLI, BONDIOLI, 2005; PROWSE, SCHWARCZ, GARNSEY, KNYF, MACCHIARELLI, BONDIOLI, 2007; PROWSE, 2001; SALVADEI, RICCI, MANZI, 2001; TAFURI, GOUDE, G. MANZI, 2018.

⁹ ARGENTI, MANZI, 1988; MANZI, SPERDUTI, 1988.

¹⁰ MANZI, SANTANDREA, PASSARELLO, 1997.

¹¹ MANZI, CENSI, SPERDUTI, PASSARELLO, 1989.

¹² ANGEL, 1966; ASCENZI, BALISTRERI, 1977; GARNSEY, 1999; SALLARES, 2002.

¹³ MANZI, SPERDUTI, PASSARELLO, 1991; CROWE, SPERDUTI, O'CONNELL, CRAIG, KIRSANOW, GERMONI, MACCHIARELLI, GARNSEY, BONDIOLI, 2010.

¹⁴ SALVADEI, RICCI, MANZI, 2001; MANZI, SALVADEI, VIENNA, PASSARELLO, 1999.

¹⁵ PROWSE, 2001; PROWSE, SCHWARCZ, SAUNDERS, MACCHIARELLI, BONDIOLI, 2004; PROWSE, SCHWARCZ, SAUNDERS, MACCHIARELLI, BONDIOLI, 2005.

different sample composition than the one considered in the present study, as it also included individuals recovered from the so-called *Campo dei Poveri* during excavations conducted in the late 1980s and early 1990s. Interestingly, isotopic evidence suggests differences in food consumption between males and females, with men generally relying more on marine resources. Isotopic analyses conducted on subadult individuals have also provided valuable information on infant feeding practices. These studies indicate that breastfeeding likely began to decline between approximately three and six months of age and was generally completed around two years of age. After weaning, children appear to have consumed diets lower in trophic level, characterised by a higher proportion of plant-based foods and secondary animal products, which may have contributed to the early development of dental pathologies such as caries and calculus¹⁶. Recent palaeopathological research has also highlighted the presence of metabolic stress markers within the population. A comparative study of Roman-period skeletal assemblages across the Empire identified several cases of vitamin D deficiency at Isola Sacra, suggesting that environmental and socio-cultural factors may have contributed to the occurrence of rickets among subadults¹⁷.

Finally, isotopic investigations of oxygen values in dental enamel have revealed significant patterns of mobility within the population. Approximately one-third of the individuals analysed show isotopic signatures suggesting non-local origins, indicating that Portus Romae attracted migrants from other regions of the Italian peninsula and possibly from more distant areas of the Empire. Importantly, the presence of non-local individuals among both adults and children suggests that migration to the harbour settlement involved entire families rather than solely male labourers¹⁸.

3. A NEW ERA OF INVESTIGATION

The study of a complex archaeological context such as the Isola Sacra necropolis poses an important methodological challenge: the integration of large amounts of heterogeneous data collected over several decades of research. To address this issue, one of the priorities of Thematic Line 03 – Bioarchaeology within Spoke 8 (Sustainability and resilience of tangible cultural heritage) of the CHANGES project was to create a comprehensive and standardised dataset capable of integrating different categories of bioarchaeological information.

Within this framework, the digital IULIA database was developed to organise and harmonise anthropological, archaeological, and biomolecular data from several skeletal collections of ancient Latium¹⁹. In addition to Isola Sacra, the database includes other key sites investigated within the project, such as *Lucus Feroniae* and Selvicciola. The aim of this initiative is to provide a unified and standardised system for documenting skeletal remains, facilitating comparative analyses, and ensuring long-term accessibility of the data.

Once this integrative framework had been established, research efforts focused on filling critical gaps in the available information in order to better contextualise the archaeological assemblage and reconstruct the life histories of the individuals buried in the necropolis. While earlier studies had primarily relied on macroscopic anthropological analyses, particularly cranial morphology and

¹⁶ PROWSE, SCHWARCZ, SAUNDERS, MACCHIARELLI, BONDIOLI, 2005.

¹⁷ MAYS, PROWSE, GEORGE, BRICKLEY, 2018.

¹⁸ PROWSE, SCHWARCZ, GARNSEY, KNYF, MACCHIARELLI, BONDIOLI, 2007.

¹⁹ FORMICHELLA, CECCONI, FARESE, MORICCA, VIGNOLA, FONSO, ROSSI, MANZI, MICARELLI, 2025.

palaeopathological observations, recent investigations have increasingly incorporated biochemical and biomolecular approaches.

These biochemical and biomolecular investigations were designed to complement and refine previous research on the population, allowing a more detailed reconstruction of diet, mobility, and biological identity. In particular, the project aimed to obtain genetic sex determination, dietary indicators, and mobility proxies for all the analysed crania. Because these analyses require destructive sampling, each specimen selected for laboratory investigation was carefully documented with detailed descriptions and high-resolution photographic records to ensure the preservation and traceability of the sampled material. This strategy also aligns the resulting dataset with the principles of FAIR data management²⁰, facilitating the findability, accessibility, and reusability of the generated information. This integrative approach provides the foundation for combining traditional osteological analyses with biomolecular evidence, ultimately enabling a more nuanced reconstruction of the life histories of the Portus population.

3.1. The biochemical analyses

To complement the osteological and palaeopathological observations, a set of biomolecular analyses was initiated within the framework of the CHANGES project in order to investigate diet, mobility, chronology, and biological sex within the harbour community of Portus Romae (Table 1). The analytical procedures have been completed or are currently ongoing, but the results are still under evaluation and are therefore not presented in this study.

Stable isotope analysis ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{15}\text{N}$, $\delta^{34}\text{S}$)

Stable carbon ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$) and nitrogen ($\delta^{15}\text{N}$) isotope analyses (IRMS) were carried out on collagen extracted from bone samples using a modified Longin protocol²¹, in order to investigate the dietary habits of the population under study. In total, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ analyses were performed on 77 individuals. For a subset of these samples ($n = 15$), sulphur isotope analyses ($\delta^{34}\text{S}$) were also conducted. These analyses were used to complement the interpretation of the carbon and nitrogen data in dietary reconstruction and to identify potential contributions of protein from aquatic environments, particularly freshwater sources²².

The quality of the extracted collagen was assessed using standard quality control parameters, including the atomic C/N ratio, collagen yield, and elemental composition, to ensure the reliability of the isotopic data obtained²³. The resulting isotopic values will be used to reconstruct dietary practices and to explore potential variation in the consumption of food resources within the analysed sample. To this end, the isotopic signatures will be compared with those from contemporary Roman and Late Antique

²⁰ WILKINSON, DUMONTIER, AALBERSBERG, APPLETON, AXTON, BAAK, 2016.

²¹ LONGIN, 1971.

²² LÖSCH, MOGHADDAM, GROSSCHMIDT, RISSER, KANZ, 2014; NEHLICH, FULLER, JAY, MORA, NICHOLSON, SMITH, RICHARDS, 2011.

²³ DENIRO, 1985; VAN KLINKEN, 1999; NEHLICH, RICHARDS, 2009.

necropolises, thereby contextualizing the Isola Sacra population within the broader dietary patterns of the period²⁴.

Radiocarbon dating (¹⁴C)

Radiocarbon dating was performed on a subset of 15 individuals included in the isotopic study in order to confirm their chronological attribution within the Imperial phases of the necropolis. By integrating radiocarbon results with the contextual information from the burial contexts, it will be possible to strengthen the temporal interpretation of the assemblage and ensure the reliability of the isotopic dataset within the broader chronological framework of the site²⁵.

Strontium isotope analysis (⁸⁷Sr/⁸⁶Sr)

Strontium isotope ratios were measured on dental enamel samples of 30 individuals to identify individuals who were local to the region and those who may have migrated from other areas of the Roman Empire. By comparing the isotopic signatures of the dental enamel with local baseline values, obtained from the analysis of dentine samples from two of the individuals selected for strontium analysis, it becomes possible to distinguish between individuals who spent their childhood in the surrounding region and those who originated from more distant locations. These data will provide new insights into patterns of mobility within the port population and the potential presence of individuals from different geographical and cultural backgrounds. The results will also contribute to a more nuanced understanding of the social dynamics, economic networks, and demographic composition of the community over time²⁶.

Amelogenin peptide analysis

As the postcranial remains could not be reliably linked to the crania recovered from Isola Sacra, biological sex was further assessed through amelogenin peptide analysis performed on dental enamel from 44 individuals. This method provides a molecular approach to sex determination and was used to verify and complement osteological sex estimations. The analytical results will be integrated with the osteological dataset in future publications²⁷.

Together, these biomolecular analyses provide complementary information on diet, mobility, chronology, and biological identity, enabling a more integrated reconstruction of the life histories of individuals buried at Isola Sacra. More importantly, this study offers a new perspective on a segment of the harbour population that has so far been investigated only through macroscopic osteological observations. By integrating legacy osteological data with new biomolecular analyses, this research

²⁴ CRAIG, BONDIOLI, FATTORE, HIGHAM, HEDGES, 2013; RICCI, SIRIGNANO, ALTIERI, PISTILLO, SANTORIELLO, LUBRITTO, 2016; CRAIG, BIAZZO, O'CONNELL, GARNSEY, MARTINEZ-LABARGA, LELLI, 2009; RUTGERS, VAN STRYDONCK, BOUDIN, VAN DER LINDE, 2009; PROWSE, SCHWARCZ, SAUNDERS, MACCHIARELLI, BONDIOLI, 2004; DUPRAS, TOCHERI, 2007; TAFURI, GOUDE, MANZI, 2018.

²⁵ CRAIG, BONDIOLI, FATTORE, HIGHAM, HEDGES, 2013; RUTGERS, VAN STRYDONCK, BOUDIN, VAN DER LINDE, 2009; ERVYNCK, BOUDIN, VAN DEN BRANDE, VAN STRYDONCK, 2014; LAFFRANCHI, GRANADOS-TORRES, LÖSCH, ZINK, DORI, DELGADO-HUERTAS, MILELLA, 2022.

²⁶ DUPRAS, SCHWARCZ, 2001; KILLGROVE, MONTGOMERY, 2016; PERRY, COLEMAN, DELHOPITAL, 2008.

²⁷ LUGLI, DI ROCCO, VAZZANA, 2019; LUGLI, FIGUS, SILVESTRINI, COSTA, BORTOLINI, CONTI, BENAZZI, 2020.

provides the first comprehensive bioarchaeological framework for reconstructing the life histories of this sector of the Portus Romae community.

Table 1: Summary of the bioarchaeological and isotopic analyses performed on the sampled individuals. The table reports the total number of individuals analysed for each method and their distribution by sex (M = male, F = female, IND = indeterminate).

Analyses	Total Individuals	M	F	IND
<i>Amelogenin peptide analysis</i>	44	26	18	0
<i>Strontium isotope analysis ($^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$)</i>	30	16	14	0
<i>Stable isotope analysis ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{15}\text{N}$)</i>	77	48	26	3
<i>Stable isotope analysis ($\delta^{34}\text{S}$)</i>	15	11	4	0
<i>Radiocarbon dating (^{14}C)</i>	15	11	4	0

4. PRELIMINARY RESULTS

The Isola Sacra population from monumental tombs was relatively homogeneous from a biological perspective. This pattern is consistent with earlier interpretations of the necropolis as representing the Portus harbour population associated with Portus Romae. The contextual information associated with the skeletal material highlights the complex depositional history of the necropolis. While some individuals can be linked to monumental funerary structures located along the *Via Flavia*, a small portion of the analysed crania derives from skeletal remains recovered without precise funerary attribution (Fig. 3).

Figure 3: Map of the monumental tombs of Isola Sacra with information on the location of males, females, and indeterminate remains in the monumental tombs.

A preliminary reconstruction of the *crania* was undertaken in order to re-associate the specimens with their original funerary contexts within the Isola Sacra necropolis. This represents the first attempt to

relocate the analysed crania within the architectural structures of the cemetery. The reconstruction required a long process of archival work aimed at tracing the original provenance of each specimen through excavation records and collection inventories.

The spatial distribution presented in Figure 3 symbolically represents the location of the individuals within the funerary monuments. Because the crania were separated from the rest of the skeletons during earlier phases of study and curation, the precise position of the skull within each tomb cannot be reconstructed with certainty. The figure, therefore, indicates the presence of individuals within specific funerary structures, rather than their exact anatomical placement within the burial.

Overall, the reconstructed sample includes 56 males, 33 females, and five individuals of indeterminate sex. In Figure 3, male individuals (blue symbols) clearly predominate in the assemblage, whereas female individuals (red symbols) are fewer in number and tend to occur in smaller clusters. A limited number of individuals of indeterminate sex (yellow symbols) are also present²⁸.

Most individuals appear concentrated in the eastern sector of the excavated area, particularly within the larger funerary structures, where multiple burials are represented. The largest monument on the far right contains the highest density of individuals, including both males and females, suggesting that these tombs were used for repeated or collective burial practices. Other monuments contain smaller groups of individuals, often composed of two to five burials.

Although the results presented here should be considered preliminary, they already highlight an important methodological contribution of this research. Beyond the biological observations themselves, the study has made it possible to reconnect a portion of the skeletal collection curated at the “G. Sergi” Museum of Anthropology with its original archaeological context within the Isola Sacra necropolis. Through the systematic integration of archival documentation, excavation records, and museum inventories, the analysed crania have been tentatively relocated within specific funerary monuments along the *Via Flavia*.

This process represents a significant step towards overcoming the long-standing disconnection between museum collections and their archaeological provenance, a situation often resulting from early excavation practices and subsequent phases of curation and study. By re-establishing these contextual relationships and integrating legacy osteological observations with newly generated biomolecular datasets within the digital IULIA database, the present research lays the groundwork for a more comprehensive and contextualised bioarchaeological interpretation of the Isola Sacra assemblage. In this sense, the contextual reconstruction presented here should be understood not only as a descriptive exercise but as the first stage in the development of a broader analytical framework aimed at reconstructing the biological characteristics, life histories, and social dynamics of the harbour settlement community associated with Portus Romae.

At present, the reconstruction provides only a general spatial framework for the distribution of the analysed crania within the necropolis. However, the existence of excavation records and individual burial forms offers the possibility of future work aimed at reconstructing the internal organization of burials within each funerary monument more precisely, potentially improving understanding of burial practices and the social composition of the groups interred in these structures.

Finally, this situation reflects the long and complex history of excavation and post-depositional disturbance at the site, including the collapse of collective burial structures and the displacement of skeletal elements within monumental tombs. As a result, the current assemblage represents not only

²⁸ FORMICHELLA, CECCONI, FARESE, MORICCA, VIGNOLA, FONSO, ROSSI, MANZI, MICARELLI, 2025.

the biological characteristics of the harbour population but also the archaeological processes that shaped the preservation and recovery of the remains.

The ongoing biomolecular analyses described above are expected to further refine these interpretations, offering additional insights into patterns of diet, mobility, and biological relationships within this complex harbour population.

5. FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Future research on the Isola Sacra population will expand current investigations through several complementary analytical approaches that are currently underway.

The first set of studies involves high-resolution stable isotope analysis of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{15}\text{N}$, and $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ from dentine microsamples, which will be used to reconstruct infant, childhood, and adolescent diet²⁹. Because dentine forms incrementally and does not remodel, these tissues provide a chronological record of dietary intake and physiological stress, allowing investigation of breastfeeding, weaning practices, and early-life dietary transitions³⁰.

In addition, ancient DNA analysis will complement the existing morphological and biochemical data. Genomic evidence will facilitate the investigation of kinship networks within the necropolis, the assessment of biological relatedness among individuals buried within the same funerary clusters, and the exploration of broader population affinities and genetic diversity within this port community³¹.

Together with ongoing osteobiographical studies integrating archaeological, biological, and biomolecular evidence, these approaches aim to provide a more comprehensive reconstruction of the life histories, biological relationships, and social dynamics of the individuals who lived and died in this densely populated port environment.

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²⁹ COCOZZA, FERNANDES, UGHI, GROB, ALEXANDER, 2021; COCOZZA, HARRIS, FORMICHELLA, PEDRUCCI, ROSSI, D'ALESSIO, AMORETTI, ZUCHTRIEGEL, O'REILLY, MANTILE, PANELLA, TAFURI, ALTIERI, DI CICCO, FERNANDES, LUBRITTO, 2025; AVERY, 2022; GANIATSOU, VIKI, GEORGIADOU, PROTOSALTI, PAPAGEORGOPOULOU, 2022.

³⁰ ALQAHTANI, HECTOR, LIVERSIDGE, 2010; HILLSON, 1996; SCHEUER, BLACK, 2004; TJÄDERHANE, CARRILHO, BRESCHI, TAY, PASHLEY, 2009; BEAUMONT, MONTGOMERY, 2015.

³¹ ANTONIO, GAO, MOOTS, LUCCI, CANDILLO, SAWYER, 2019; COIA, PALADIN, ZINGALE, WURST, CROZE, MAIXNER, ZINK, 2023; DE ANGELIS, SCORRANO, MARTÍNEZ-LABARGA, SCANO, MACCIARDI, RICKARDS, 2018; DE ANGELIS, ROMBONI, VELTRE, CATALANO, MARTÍNEZ-LABARGA, GAZZANIGA, RICKARDS, 2022.

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